

Research Article

Evaluation of Polyphenol and Flavonoid Content of Honey from Central and Southern Romania

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Abstract

In this study, 10 types of honey were used according to their botanical origin: acacia (*Robinia pseudoacacia* L.), lime tree (*Tilia × europaea* L.), rapeseed (*Brassica napus* L.), polyfloral, fir, meadow, Japanese knotweed (*Reynoutria japonica*), mountain, heather (*Calluna vulgaris*) and raspberry (*Rubus idaeus*). These honey types were obtained from a single beekeeper and were harvested in 2022, 2023 and 2024, from the intra-Carpathian area (Transylvania) and southern Romania. Honey samples were analyzed for total phenols and flavonoids content. The concentrations of total phenols and flavonoids were different depending on the year of harvesting. Heating the samples (from 20 to 90°C) resulted in variation of these compounds. Studies on the physicochemical characteristics of honey should be continued in order to select the most suitable type of honey for the realization of functional products based on this natural product.

Keywords: Botanical origin; Chemical analysis; Temperature; Total polyphenols

Introduction

Honey is a substance naturally produced by honey bees (*Apis mellifera* L.) from flower nectar and honeydew [1]. Dictionaries define honey as a semi-liquid, yellowish, sweet and aromatic substance, very rich in sugars, vitamins and enzymes, collected and produced by bees from flower nectar. The Codex Alimentarius provides a comprehensive definition: a sweet natural substance produced by honey bees from the nectar of plants or from secretions of living parts of

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plants and honeydew—a sugary excretion left on plants by sap-sucking insects. Bees collect these materials, transform them with their own enzymes, deposit, dehydrate, store and allow them to mature in honeycombs. Bees also add their own specific substances during the honey making process [2-4].

Since ancient times, honey has been used not only as food but also as medicine for treating or alleviating various conditions, including heart disease, infected or chronic wounds, nervous system disorders, gastrointestinal disorders, gingivitis, bronchial asthma, and eye conditions [5-7].

Its nutritional and therapeutic properties are due to its highly diverse composition—honey contains at least 200 substances [8]. Honey consists mainly of sugars (80-85 %), with fructose and glucose being the major components. It also contains a variety of minor components such as proteins, enzymes, organic acids, minerals, phenolic compounds and vitamins, all of which determine its sensory and functional characteristics [9]. Thus, with a water content of 15-18%, honey is a concentrated carbohydrate solution that includes many bioactive compounds [10,11].

The functional characteristics of honey are due to the presence of antioxidant compounds: phenolic compounds (flavonoids, phenolic acids), vitamins (C, E), and enzymes (catalase, peroxidase) [12-14]. The composition and properties of honey depend on floral and geographical origin, bee species, harvest season (spring or summer), environmental factors, and storage conditions [15-18].

The present work analyses and compares the main physicochemical characteristics of 10 commercial honey types from the intra-Carpathian region and the rest of Romania, focusing on the principal quality parameters.

Materials and Methods

Ten honey types were studied according to floral origin: acacia (*Robinia pseudoacacia* L.), lime tree (*Tilia × europaea* L.), rapeseed (*Brassica napus* L.), polyfloral, fir, meadow, Japanese knotweed (*Reynoutria japonica*), mountain, heather (*Calluna vulgaris*), and raspberry (*Rubus idaeus*). All honey came from the same beekeeper and was harvested in 2022, 2023, and 2024 from the intra-Carpathian region (Transylvania) and southern Romania. Consistency and color characteristics were typical for each honey type (Table 1).

Analyses were performed using 10% honey solutions in distilled water. All determinations were carried out in triplicate. Using this dilution, the total content of polyphenols and flavonoids was measured. Results are expressed as mean ± standard deviation. Given the importance of phenolic compounds in honey, analyses were also performed to assess the influence of temperature and harvest year on total phenols and flavonoids.

Determination of Total Phenolic Content

0.25mL of aqueous extract was combined with 1mL 1M sodium carbonate and 1.25mL Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. After 15min, optical

Type of Honey	Floral Origin	Geographic Origin	Consistency	Color
Acacia	Monofloral, Robinia pseudoacacia L.	Southern Romania(a) / Transylvania(b)	Fluid	Pale yellow
Lime tree	Monofloral, Tilia × europaea L.	Transylvania	Crystallized	Amber
Rapeseed	Monofloral, Brassica napus L.	Southern Romania	Crystallized	Cream
Meadow	Polyfloral	Transylvania	Fluid	Orange
Polyfloral	Polyfloral	Southern Romania	Partially Crystallized	Deep yellow
Heather	Monofloral, Calluna vulgaris	Transylvania	Gelified	Reddish brown
Mountain	Polyfloral/extrafloral	Transylvania	Fluid	Dark brown
Fir	Extrafloral	Transylvania	Fluid	Dark brown
Japanese Knotweed	Monofloral, Reynoutria japonica	Transylvania	Fluid	Light brown
Raspberry	Monofloral/extrafloral	Transylvania	Fluid	Brown

Table 1: Honey types included in the study.

Note: Honey was packaged in glass jars and stored in the dark at 18-24°C [19].

density was measured at 765nm (1cm cuvette) against a blank. Results were expressed as µg gallic acid/g honey [20].

Determination of Flavonoid Content

The visible-range method is based on complexation of flavonoids with aluminum chloride (AlCl₃) in an environment of sodium acetate. 0.1mL 10% AlCl₃ was added to 0.5 mL sample or standard, followed by 0.1mL 1M CH₃COONa and 2.8mL distilled water. After vigorous mixing and 10 minutes at room temperature, absorbance was read at 415nm against a blank (AlCl₃ replaced by water). Quercetin 100 µM was used as standard [21].

Influence of Temperature on Total Polyphenol and Flavonoid Content

10% honey dilutions were heated for 15min at 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, and 90°C. The total content in polyphenols and flavonoids was determined after cooling to room temperature.

Spectrophotometric measurements were performed using a Cam-spec M105 spectrophotometer (wavelength range 335-1000nm, accuracy ±1% between 0-1A).

Results

Total Phenolic Content

Among the studied samples, mountain honey had the highest total phenolic content (6112.88µg/g), followed by fir and heather honey (both >5000µg/g). Raspberry and Japanese knotweed honeys also had high levels. Both samples of acacia honey showed very low contents (882.9µg/g (a) and 1177.59µg/g (b)). Rapeseed and polyfloral honey also exhibited low phenolic content. Honeys from the intra-Carpathian region (fir, mountain, meadow, heather) generally showed the highest phenolic levels (Figure 1).

Cluj and Sălaj counties (Transylvania) are Romania's most important area for Japanese knotweed honey [22]. Conifer honeydew honey is, together with heather honey, the most expensive variety on the Polish market [23]. A comparative study of acacia, lime tree,

Figure 1: Total phenolic content in honeys of different floral origins.

Note: Values are means of three determinations ± SD.

sunflower, and honeydew honeys showed that honeydew honey had the highest phenolic content, while among floral honeys sunflower honey was richest [24]. Phenolic composition varies greatly depending on botanical, geographical, and entomological origin [25,26].

Flavonoid Content

Mountain honey again showed elevated flavonoid content, followed by heather and Japanese knotweed honeys. Rapeseed, polyfloral, meadow, and both acacia honey samples (a & b) had the lowest flavonoid levels (Figure 2).

Common flavonoids in honey are quercetin [27] and luteolin [28].

Influence of Harvest Year on Total Content of Polyphenols and Flavonoids

Acacia (a), rapeseed, and polyfloral honeys harvested in three consecutive years (2022, 2023, 2024) were analyzed. Polyphenol and flavonoid contents varied annually for each honey type (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Flavonoid content in honeys of different floral origins.

Note: Values are means of three determinations ± SD.

Figure 3: Total phenolics (left) and flavonoids (right) in honeys of different floral origins according to harvest year.

Note: Values are means of three determinations ± SD.

Influence of Temperature on Total Phenolic Content

Total phenolic concentration was affected by heating temperature. Fir, meadow, Japanese knotweed, mountain, and heather honeys showed good stability between 50-90°C. Rapeseed and polyfloral honeys fluctuated but returned to near-initial values at 90°C. Acacia honeys behaved similarly, with acacia (a) showing a faster increase in polyphenols compared to acacia (b), which had a higher initial content. (Figure 4 & Table 2).

Heat treatments generally reduce honey quality by degrading polyphenols and volatile compounds, decreasing enzymatic activity, and darkening color [17,29]. However, Vietnamese honey showed up to 28 % increase in phenolics when heated to 90°C [30]. Longan honey heated to 50-70°C for 5min exhibited highest phenolic and flavonoid contents due to improved extraction [31].

Influence of Temperature on Flavonoid Content

All honey types showed increased flavonoid content with heating (Figure 5). The largest increases were observed in rapeseed honey (4.84×), acacia (a) (5.77×), and acacia (b) (3.37×) when comparing 90°C with 20°C (Table 3).

Heating of various Indonesian honeys also increased flavonoid levels, with differences depending on geographical origin and bee species [32].

Statistical Analysis

Overall, all honey types showed a smooth but statistically significant increase in both phenol and flavonoid content as heat treatments

Figure 4: Influence of temperature on total phenolic content.

Note: Values are means of three determinations ± SD.

Honey Type	Polyphenol Content (µg/g)		Polyphenol Content Ratio Between 90°C and 20°C
	20°C	90°C	
Acacia (a)	882.95	1316.7	1.49
Acacia (b)	1177.59	1546.17	1.31
Rapeseed	2144.78	2076.82	0.96
Polyfloral	1765.75	2032.38	1.15
Japanese knotweed	3799.46	3809.92	1.00
Lime tree	2042.84	2139.55	1.04
Raspberry	3817.76	3574.66	0.93
Heather	4913.04	4622.88	0.94
Fir	5273.77	5430.62	1.02
Mountain	6112.88	6005.70	0.98
Meadow	2306.85	2539.50	1.10

Table 2: Ratio of total phenolic content at 90°C versus room temperature (20°C).

Figure 5: Influence of temperature on flavonoid content.

Note: Values are means of three determinations ± SD.

Honey Type	Flavonoid Content (µg/g)		Polyphenol Content Ratio Between 90°C and 20°C
	20°C	90°C	
Acacia (a)	0.18	1.04	5.77
Acacia (b)	0.40	1.36	3.37
Rapeseed	1.58	7.69	4.84
Polyfloral	2.67	4.14	1.54
Japanese knotweed	8.04	15.08	1.84
Lime tree	2.38	3.18	1.33
Raspberry	4.81	6.51	1.35
Heather	7.79	14.92	1.91
Fir	6.12	9.01	1.46
Mountain	10.18	20.54	2.01
Meadow	3.09	9.54	3.09

Table 3: Ratio of flavonoid content at 90°C versus room temperature (20°C).

were applied. Both types of acacia honey presented a high increase in both polyphenol and flavonoid contents, while rapeseed honey showed a fairly stable polyphenol content but a high increase in flavonoids. (Tables 4-14).

Source	S ²	DF	MS	F	P	ng ²	eps
Polyphenol Content							
Temperature	565425.8	7	80775.11	911.4477	1.62E-17	0.997274	0.264538
Error	1240.72	14	88.62287				
Flavonoid Content							
Temperature	2.139224	7	0.305603	68.57266	9.33E-10	0.967554	0.170751
Error	0.062393	14	0.004457				

Table 4: One way ANOVA of acacia honey (a)

Source	S ²	DF	MS	F	P	ng ²	eps
Polyphenol Content							
Temperature	348221.5	7	49745.93	280.7741	5.90E-14	0.985611	0.232991
Error	2480.439	14	177.1742				
Flavonoid Content							
Temperature	4.384246	7	0.626321	122.9678	1.76E-11	0.979445	0.222506
Error	0.071307	14	0.005093				

Table 5: One way ANOVA of acacia honey (b)

Source	S ²	DF	MS	F	P	ng ²	eps
Polyphenol Content							
Temperature	1244436	7	177776.5	173.8791	1.62E-12	0.988472	0.246522

Source	S ²	DF	MS	F	P	ng ²	eps
Error	14313.81	14	1022.415				
Flavonoid Content							
Temperature	100.6639	7	14.38056	1862.237	1.10E-19	0.993462	0.269336
Error	0.108111	14	0.007722				

Table 6: One way ANOVA of rapeseed honey.

Source	S ²	DF	MS	F	P	ng ²	eps
Polyphenol Content							
Temperature	1468292	7	209756	144.7316	5.74E-12	0.986243	0.257448
Error	20289.86	14	1449.276				
Flavonoid Content							
Temperature	20.1669	7	2.880986	238.0267	1.85E-13	0.986202	0.210813
Error	0.169451	14	0.012104				

Table 7: One way ANOVA of polyfloral honey.

Source	S ²	DF	MS	F	P	ng ²	eps
Polyphenol Content							
Temperature	359795.5	7	51399.36	172.7066	1.70E-12	0.980558	0.197179
Error	4166.552	14	297.6109				
Flavonoid Content							
Temperature	194.316	7	27.75943	980.3856	9.76E-18	0.997889	0.211794
Error	0.396407	14	0.028315				

Table 8: One way ANOVA of Japanese knotweed honey.

Source	S ²	DF	MS	F	P	ng ²	eps
Polyphenol Content							
Temperature	1087782	7	155397.5	352.8748	1.21E-14	0.993857	0.213615
Error	6165.261	14	440.3758				
Flavonoid Content							
Temperature	2.58086 122.0228 98	7	0.368694	47.74464	1.05E-08	0.93552	0.197109
Error	0.108111	14	0.007722				

Table 9: One way ANOVA of lime tree honey.

Source	S ²	DF	MS	F	P	ng ²	eps
Polyphenol Content							
Temperature	1723880	7	246268.5	705.9312	9.66E-17	0.996941	0.256307

Error	4883.988	14	348.8563					
Flavonoid Content								
Temperature	10.74668 122.0228 98	7	1.535241	102.6813	6.03E-11	0.976589	0.261514	
Error	0.209321	14	0.014952					

Table 10: One way ANOVA of raspberry honey.

Source	S ²	DF	MS	F	P	ng ²	eps
Polyphenol Content							
Temperature	726336.5	7	103762.4	247.1303	1.43E-13	0.991715	0.274723
Error	5878.166	14	419.869				
Flavonoid Content							
Temperature	122.0228 122.0228 98	7	17.43182	763.2806	5.60E-17	0.997193	0.263347
Error	0.319732	14	0.022838				

Table 11: One way ANOVA of heather honey.

Source	S ²	DF	MS	F	P	ng ²	eps
Polyphenol Content							
Temperature	273000.9	7	39000.13	216.1051	3.62E-13	0.990333	0.267663
Error	2526.556	14	180.4683				
Flavonoid Content							
Temperature	19.38598	7	2.769425	206.3961	4.97E-13	0.988737	0.284006
Error	0.187852	14	0.013418				

Table 12: One way ANOVA of fir honey.

Source	S ²	DF	MS	F	P	ng ²	eps
Polyphenol Content							
Temperature	421547.6	7	60221.08	18.37095	4.75E-06	0.893854	0.169313
Error	45892.85	14	3278.06				
Flavonoid Content							
Temperature	298.8998	7	42.69997	653.5265	1.65E-16	0.994652	0.156224
Error	0.914729	14	0.065338				

Table 13: One way ANOVA of mountain honey.

Source	S ²	DF	MS	F	P	ng ²	eps
Polyphenol Content							
Temperature	185558.3	7	26508.33	120.4897	2.02E-11	0.983485	0.20945
Error	3080.07	14	220.005				
Flavonoid Content							

Temperature	160.9729	7	22.99614	2624.295	1.00E-20	0.999238	0.267023
Error	0.122679	14	0.008763				

Table 14: One way ANOVA of meadow honey.

Discussion

Total phenolic and flavonoid contents varied among the analyzed honeys depending on floral origin and harvest year.

Total phenolic content was influenced by heating temperature (20-90°C) and showed fluctuating behavior. Acacia honey from southern Romania displayed the largest increase in phenolics at 90°C.

Flavonoid content also showed similar behavior in acacia honeys (both regions) and rapeseed honey, with the highest ratios between 90°C and 20°C.

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